

Peptide alkaloids of *Zizyphus rugosa*

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Abstract : Five cyclopeptide alkaloids, sativanine-C, mauritine-A, mauritine-D, amphibine-B and nummularine-K has been isolated from the bark of *Zizyphus rugosa* and their structures were established by spectral evidences. This is the first report of these compounds in *Z. rugosa*.

Keywords : *Zizyphus rugosa*, cyclopeptide alkaloids.

Introduction

The plant *Zizyphus rugosa* Lam. (Family : Rhamnaceae) is distributed throughout greater parts of India. The plant is commonly used in Indian medicine for the treatment of diarrhea and menorrhagia¹. A number of cyclopeptide alkaloids viz. franguloline², nummularine-P³, rugosanine-A⁴, rugosanine-B³, sativanine-H³ and amphibine-D⁵ have earlier been reported from this plant. We here report the isolation of five cyclopeptide alkaloids from the bark of *Z. rugosa* which has not earlier been reported from this plant.

Experimental

The bark of the plant *Zizyphus rugosa* was collected from Mirzapur District, Uttar Pradesh, India and identified from the Department of Botany, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi. Dried and powdered barks (3.5 kg) were repeatedly extracted with a mixture of C₆H₆-NH₄OH-MeOH (100 : 1 : 1). The total extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and then extracted with 7% aqueous citric acid. The acidic solution was basified with ammonia and extracted thoroughly with CHCl₃. The CHCl₃ fraction was evaporated to dryness which furnished a brown semi-solid crude base fraction. The crude base fraction was chromatographed over SiO₂ gel column eluting with a mixture of CHCl₃ and MeOH. The eluants collected from CHCl₃, CHCl₃-MeOH (9 : 1), (8 : 2), (7 : 3) and (2 : 1), on evaporation followed by crystallization of the residues from MeOH furnished, respectively,

the cyclopeptide alkaloids, sativanine-C⁶ (15 mg) (**1**) as colourless granules, m.p. 264–265 °C; mauritine-A⁷ (20 mg) (**2**) as colourless granules, m.p. 103–104 °C; mauritine-D⁸ (21 mg) (**3**) as amorphous powder; amphibine-B⁹ (18 mg) (**4**) as amorphous powder and nummularine-K¹⁰ (22 mg) (**5**) as colourless granules, m.p. 237–239 °C.

Sativanine-C (**1**) : It exhibited UV λ_{\max} (MeOH) nm : 205 (strong end absorption); IR ν_{\max} (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3260 (-NH), 3020–2920 (-CH), 2890, 2790 (-NCH₃), 1652 (sec. amido group), 1624 (-C=C-), 1610, 1500 (aromatic), 1230 (phenol ether); MS : *m/z* 534.3220 ([M⁺], HRMS, calcd. for : C₃₁H₄₂N₄O₄ 534.3205), 489, 308, 228, 218, 190, 148, 135, 131, 115, 114.1288 (C₇H₁₆N, base peak). Hydrolysis of **1** with 6 N HCl in a sealed tube for 20 h at 120 °C furnished two ninhydrin positive spots in the hydrolysate identified as phenylalanine and *N,N*-dimethylisoleucine by co-PC with authentic samples.

Mauritine-A (**2**) : It exhibited UV λ_{\max} (MeOH) nm : 203 (strong end absorption); IR ν_{\max} (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3395 (-NH), 2960–2820 (-CH), 2790 (-NCH₃), 1660 (sec. amido group), 1620 (-C=C-), 1220, 1040 (phenol ether); MS : *m/z* 575.3187 ([M⁺], HRMS, calcd. for : C₃₂H₄₁N₅O₆ 575.3107), 574, 546, 532, 530, 504, 502, 461, 378, 377, 376, 328, 308, 243, 229, 221, 215, 199, 186, 171, 135, 96, 72.0816 (C₄H₁₀N, base peak). Hydrolysis of **2** with 6 N HCl in a sealed tube for 20 h at 120 °C furnished two ninhydrin positive spots in the hydrolysate identified as

phenylalanine and *N,N*-dimethylalanine by co-PC with authentic samples.

Mauritine-D (3) : It exhibited UV λ_{\max} (MeOH) nm : 235 (strong end absorption); IR ν_{\max} (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3300 (-NH), 3010–2870 (-CH), 2790 (-NCH₃), 1690 (sec. amido group), 1630 (-C=C-), 1600 and 1500 (aromatic), 1214 and 1025 (phenol ether); MS : *m/z* 597.3939 ([M⁺], HRMS, calcd. for : C₃₃H₅₁N₅O₅ 597.3929), 540, 484, 441, 371, 370, 344, 343, 342, 324, 274, 255, 235, 229, 227, 209, 203, 186, 181, 135, 114.1284 (C₇H₁₆N, base peak), 96, 86, 68. Hydrolysis of **3** with 6 *N* HCl in a sealed tube for 20 h at 120 °C furnished three ninhydrin spots in the hydrolysate identified as leucine, isoleucine and *N,N*-dimethylisoleucine by co-PC with authentic samples.

Amphibine-B (4) : It exhibited UV λ_{\max} (MeOH) nm : 210 (strong end absorption) and 260 sh; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3350–3200 (-NH), 2790 (-NCH₃), 1680, 1640 (sec. amido group), 1620 (-C=C-), 1220 (phenol ether); MS : *m/z* 665.3587 ([M⁺], HRMS, calcd. for : C₃₉H₄₇N₅O₅ 665.3576), 663, 622, 574, 518, 378, 376, 308, 243, 229, 215, 209, 203, 186, 148.1128 (C₁₀H₁₄N, base peak). Hydrolysis of **4** with 6 *N* HCl in a sealed tube for 20 h at 120 °C furnished three ninhydrin positive spots in the hydrolysate identified as isoleucine, phenylalanine and *N,N*-dimethylphenylalanine by co-PC with authentic samples.

Nummularine-K (5) : It exhibited UV λ_{\max} (MeOH) nm : 223 (strong end absorption), 290 sh, 281 sh, and 273 sh; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3270 (-NH), 2980–2830 (-CH), 2785 (-NCH₃), 1675, 1625 (sec. amido group), 1610 (-C=C-), 1230 and 980 (phenol ether); MS : *m/z* 573.3284 ([M⁺], HRMS, calcd. for : C₃₃H₄₃N₅O₄ 573.3286), 443, 387, 303, 274, 195, 190, 187.1338 (C₁₂H₁₅N₂, base peak), 182, 167, 135, 130, 97, 86. Hydrolysis of **5** with 6 *N* HCl in a sealed tube for 20 h at 120 °C furnished two ninhydrin positive spots in the

hydrolysate identified as 3-hydroxyleucine and leucine by co-PC comparison with authentic samples. Compound **5** was further hydrolysed with Ba(OH)₂ for 22 h at 120 °C which furnished one Ehrlich's reagent positive spots in the hydrolysate identified as *N,N*-dimethyltryptophan by co-PC with authentic sample.

The spectral data of all the compounds (**1-5**) tallies with the reported data. The structures were further confirmed by direct comparison with authentic samples (m.m.p., co-TLC and superimposable IR).

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References

1. K. R. Kirtikar and B. D. Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants", Lalit Mohan Basu, Allahabad, 1975, Vol. 1, p. 594.
2. Y. C. Tripathi, Dissertation "Chemistry of Medicinal Plants", Department of Medicinal Chemistry, Banaras Hindu University, 1988, pp. 128-129.
3. Y. C. Tripathi, S. K. Maurya, V. P. Singh and V. B. Pandey, *Phytochemistry*, 1989, **28**, 1563.
4. V. B. Pandey, Y. C. Tripathi, S. Devi, J. P. Singh and A. H. Shah, *Phytochemistry*, 1988, **27**, 1915.
5. R. Tschesche, A. H. Shah, V. B. Pandey, J. P. Singh, M. V. Radloff and G. Eckhardt, *Die Pharmazie*, 1981, **36**, 511.
6. R. Tschesche and E. Ammermann, *Ber.*, 1974, **100**, 323.
7. R. Tschesche, H. Wilhelm and W. H. Fehlhaber, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1972, 2609.
8. R. Tschesche, H. Wilhelm, E. U. Kausmann and G. Eckhardt, *Ann.*, 1974, 1694.
9. R. Tschesche, E. U. Kausmann and W. H. Fehlhaber, *Ber.*, 1972, **105**, 3094.
10. R. Tschesche, M. Elgamal and G. Eckhardt, *Chem. Ber.*, 1977, **110**, 2649.